

ADVANCED INTEGRATED GENERAL AVIATION PRIMARY FLIGHT DISPLAY USER INTERFACE DESIGN, DEVELOPMENT AND ASSESSMENT

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Abstract

This article describes work performed during a project in the Master of Engineering degree program in the Department of Aeronautics and Astronautics of the Massachusetts Institute of Technology. It was performed in close coordination with the Avidyne Corporation of Bedford, Massachusetts and involved design, development and assessment of the user interface for a primary flight display (PFD)/ horizontal situation indicator (HSI). Software interfaces were developed using various techniques including the Goals, Operators, Methods, Selection Rules (GOMS) Keystroke-Level Model. A human subject evaluation using a personal computer based simulation resulted in quantitative and qualitative results that indicate significant gains over a recent prototype. Improvements to the user interface were made in several areas including task execution time, accuracy and a subjective comparison of ease of use. Over the six common tasks, the mean task execution time for the baseline display was 37.6 seconds compared with 23.6 seconds and 22.2 seconds for two alternative user interfaces. In addition the accuracy of setting the standby NAV format task was significantly better in the new user interfaces. In a redundant paired comparison of the three interfaces based upon ease of use, the new interfaces were significantly better than the baseline. The application of the GOMS Keystroke-Level Model to primary flight display user interface design was validated through the human subject evaluation. Project outcomes support the Avidyne product development goal of fielding the first 'Highway-in-the-Sky' (HITS) flight display for general aviation applications.

Introduction

The focus of this effort was the design, development and assessment of the user interface for a primary flight display/horizontal situation indicator intended for general aviation use. Another

goal of this effort was the eventual integration of Highway-in-the-Sky (HITS) technology.

The goal of HITS technology is to significantly increase utility, safety and ease-of-flying. Affordable glass cockpit technology will provide pilots with direct access to all information needed to safely determine their routes, speeds, proximity to adverse weather conditions, terrain and other aircraft.

The Avidyne Corporation sponsored this effort and all work was done in close coordination with Avidyne engineers. Avidyne is an avionics industry leader with innovative products that greatly enhance pilots' situational awareness and safety during every phase of flight. Avidyne's goal is to provide an affordable glass cockpit to the general aviation market so that pilots may benefit from the increased safety and ease-of-use brought about by Avidyne's technology and effective design.

Background

The primary flight display includes the information most critical for safe flight. It includes the flight instruments that are located on the screen in the same traditional "T" configuration of conventional analog flight instruments. The PFD is normally centered directly in front of the pilot since this is the most critical and often referenced display. Typical user interface tasks performed on the PFD include setting various reference markers or bugs for desired parameters such as heading or altitude, selecting navigation sources and formats and adjusting the map display clutter and range scale.

Development of the Primary Flight Display (PFD) Hardware

The development of the PFD hardware was critical to the success of the user interface and was done in close coordination with the software interface development. The PFD hardware configuration emerged based upon the efforts of an

Figure 1. Primary Flight Display Hardware Configuration

industrial design firm in conjunction with the results of the flight test of a demonstration unit as well as application of the Goals, Operators, Methods, Selection Rules (GOMS) Keystroke-Level Model. These efforts are described in reference [1]. The selected hardware configuration is shown in Figure 1. The hardware controls include five software-programmable buttons on the left and right sides as well as two dual concentric knobs (also software programmable) at the lower corners. On/off and brightness functions have dedicated controls.

Required User Interface Tasks

The required user interface tasks are listed below and are grouped according to function.

Map Adjustment Tasks

- Adjust the range (RNG) (9 settings)
- Select the declutter setting (5 settings)
- Select the view setting (3 settings)

Navigation Display Tasks

- Set the active NAV display course (CRS)

- Sync the active CRS to the current heading
- Set the standby (Stby) NAV display course
- Sync the standby CRS to the current heading
- Select the source for the active NAV display (4 settings)
- Select the format for the standby NAV display (4 settings)
- Select the source for the auxiliary NAV display (5 settings)
- Swap the active and stby NAV displays

Bug and Barometer Setting Tasks

- Set the baro altimeter setting
- Sync the baro setting to 29.92
- Set the altitude (ALT) bug
- Sync the ALT bug to the current ALT
- Set the heading (HDG) bug
- Sync the HDG bug to the current HDG

In accordance with the system requirements, the following tasks will have dedicated controls and so will not be placed into functional groups:

- Select the mode (Normal and Backup)
- Adjust the brightness

Description of Tasks

For a description of tasks see reference [2].

User Interface Human Subject Evaluation

Test subjects completed a series of tasks using three interface configurations to evaluate the configurations and validate the GOMS Keystroke-Level Model time predictions. Both the original demonstration configuration (Version A) and two alternative configurations (Versions B and C) were evaluated in order to determine if there were any performance gains and to capture subjective feedback for design improvements. Versions B and C were developed as a result of feedback from flight tests of the demonstration configuration and application of the GOMS keystroke-level model.

Experimental Setup

The selected hardware configuration landscape-oriented bezel was not yet operational at the time of the evaluation so the new configurations were adapted to the an existing portrait-oriented bezel. Unfortunately the portrait-oriented bezel has only one dual concentric knob without a push button capability. The use of this bezel prevented all tasks from being fully evaluated. Six tasks common to all three configurations were evaluated and could be directly compared. Six additional tasks were evaluated three of which were directly comparable between A and B and three were directly comparable between A and C. The synchronization tasks could not be accomplished in versions B or C and so were not evaluated. The same electronic flight instrument displays were used in all three versions to eliminate any bias from the displays.

Version A

The original demonstration user interface is shown in Figure 2. This interface was used as a baseline for comparison to determine if any significant improvements were made.

Figure 2. User Interface Version A (Demonstration Configuration)

Version B

This version was the redesigned user interface optimized for operation with dual Garmin GNS 430s and a landscape orientation. Minor changes were made to adapt the newly designed interface to the portrait-oriented Avrotec bezel as shown in Figure 3. In general the simplified navigation display tasks are on the left and the bug and baro setting tasks are on the right. Map adjustment tasks are located on the left dual concentric knob (not evaluated due to a hardware limitation).

Figure 3. User Interface Version B (Map Controls on Left Knob)

Version C

This configuration was similar to Version B except that the map adjustment tasks are on the right side buttons and the bug and baro setting tasks are split between the two dual concentric knobs. Heading and course tasks are accomplished with the left knob while the altitude bug and baro setting tasks are accomplished with the right knob. The left and right knobs default to heading and baro respectively. Course or altitude bug mode can be selected by pressing the button immediately above the knob. The knobs will remain in this mode as long as there are inputs to the knob, however they will default to heading and baro after five seconds without inputs. The concept is that the heading and baro tasks will be used more frequently and it will enable the user to have dedicated knobs for these tasks similar to a conventional cockpit. Version C is pictured in Figure 4.

Figure 4. User Interface Version C (Map Controls on the Right Side Buttons)

Protocol

To mitigate the effects of learning, the interface configurations were presented in a counterbalanced order. Before the experiment, the pilots were trained on the use of the interface and the flight displays. They were given an opportunity to fly the displays and conduct practice tasks until they felt comfortable with the displays and what was expected of them. The Avrotec hardware was networked with a computer running Microsoft Flight Simulator 2000 to provide flight inputs. Subjects flew the simulator with their left hand using a standard joystick. Subjects were required to use their left hand since the design aircraft has a left side-stick controller and to induce additional workload. Subjects were required to maintain a constant heading, airspeed and altitude while completing the user interface tasks to induce workload and distract them from the primary task. Subjects completed 13 tasks in Version A and 9 tasks each in Versions B and C in random order. Each task was evaluated twice for a total of 26 in Version A and 18 in Versions B and C. The simulator setup is shown below.

(The Microsoft Flight Simulator screen was not visible to the subjects while conducting the experiment.)

Figure 5. Simulator Setup

Results of the Interface Design Experiment

The experiment was conducted from the end of April to early May 2001. The subject profile is discussed first, followed by the results of the experiment.

Subject Profile

A total of six instrument rated pilots from the General Aviation community took part in the study. The age of the group ranged between 26 and 53, with an average of 37 and a standard deviation of 9.6 years. Two were female, representing 33% of the subject pool.

Three of the six pilots were Certified Flight Instructors qualified to teach instruments. The six pilots had an average of 1686 flight hours. Only one pilot had rated military experience (two had non-rated military flight engineer experience). None of the subjects had any significant prior glass cockpit display experience.

Performance Metrics

Performance metrics include the task execution time, accuracy, corrected error rate, uncorrected error rate, control input efficiency and subjective workload. In addition, the secondary flying tasks of maintaining assigned heading, airspeed and altitude were also analyzed for statistical significance. Finally the predicted mean execution time based on the GOMS Keystroke-Level Model was compared to the actual mean execution time.

Task Execution Time

Execution times were recorded for each task by the computer. Time began when the subject moved their hand from the start position on the table (based on a key input from the evaluator) and ended with the last control input.

An ANOVA of the mean execution times was conducted to determine if the mean execution times were significantly different between versions. The tasks that were evaluated in all three versions are shown in figure 6. The mean execution time of the altitude bug setting task in Versions B and C was significantly shorter ($p < 0.05$) than in Version A. There was no significant difference in the altitude bug setting task between Versions B and C. Similarly the standby NAV format task was significantly shorter ($p < 0.05$) in Versions B and C than in Version A. Again there was no significant difference for this task between Versions B and C.

The tasks that can be directly compared between Versions A and B and A and C are shown in Figures 7 and 8 respectively.

An ANOVA of the tasks common to Versions A and B revealed a significantly shorter mean execution time in version B of the heading bug task ($p < 0.05$) and the active NAV course task ($p < 0.05$).

The differences in the mean execution times between Versions A and C were not statistically significant at the 5% level ($p > 0.05$).

Figure 6. Mean Execution Time Including Errors for Versions A, B and C

Figure 7. Mean Execution Time Including Errors for Versions A and B

Figure 8. Mean Execution Time Including Errors for Versions A and C

Figure 9. Accuracy Comparison Between Versions A, B and C

Task Accuracy

Accuracy of the various tasks was determined by dividing the total number of times a task was correctly performed by the total number of times the task was performed. A correctly performed task was considered one where no extra control inputs were made. Tasks are organized into three groups: the tasks performed in Versions A, B and C (Figure 9); the tasks performed in Versions A and B (Figure 10); and the tasks performed in Versions A and C (Figure 11).

Accuracy differences between the versions were tested for significance by determining the standard deviation using the following formula:

$$p(1-p) / n^{1/2}$$

where p is the proportion correct and "n" is the sample size of each task. The largest standard deviation among the three common tasks was then used. Differences were considered significant if the difference between versions was greater than three times the largest standard deviation ($p < 0.01$). Based on this criterion, the standby NAV format

task was significantly more accurate in Versions B and C than in Version A.

The implementation of the active NAV course task was significantly more accurate in Version B than in Version A as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Accuracy Comparison Between Versions A and B

Execution of the range task was significantly more accurate in Version C than in Version A as shown in Figure 11. The only difference between these two tasks was that in Version A the user must first move to a submenu.

Figure 11. Accuracy Comparison Between Versions A and C

Error Rate

There were two types of errors recorded during the experiment, corrected and uncorrected errors. A corrected error is one in which the user recognized the error and eventually correctly performed the task. The most common example of this was toggling past the desired setting. Task error rates that are statistically different are the same ones determined in the accuracy analysis.

Control Input Efficiency

Control input efficiency was determined by dividing the minimum number of control inputs required to perform a task by the actual number of control inputs used. Setting a dual-concentric knob to a desired value was treated as one control input for this calculation. In order to make direct comparisons, only the six tasks evaluated in all three versions were considered. The results are shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Control Input Efficiency

Versions A and B had an efficiency nearly 10% higher than that of Version C although this difference was not statistically significant. Efficiencies of Versions A and B were nearly the same, although it took over twice the number of control inputs in version A (323) to accomplish these same tasks as in Version B (150).

Results of Paired Comparison

Each of the six subjects rated each of the three versions against each other based upon ease of use. The Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) utilizing redundant paired comparisons yielded a relative ranking between the alternatives as shown in Figure 13 [3].

Figure 13. Results of Paired Comparison

Based on these comparisons Version A was easier to use than either Versions B or C, but there was no statistically significant difference between Versions B and C.

Subjective Feedback

An analysis of the subjective feedback for common comments revealed the following trends:

All six subjects reported confusion between the “HSI SRC” and “SRC SEL” labels of Versions B and C. The labels did not convey any meaning to the subjects and they felt they had to memorize the function of the buttons rather than rely on the labels to remind them of their functions.

Four subjects preferred having all of the knob mode options displayed as in Version B. All of the knob functions were easily visible at all times. In Version A the pilots had to toggle through options and were “surprised” as each option appeared and often would toggle pass the desired option.

Four subjects expressed a preference for having the map controls on the top level. Again having map controls on the top level provided continuous visibility of these tasks.

Half of the subjects thought the “Map” label was confusing and recommended “Declutter.” “Map” did not convey any useful meaning to the subjects. They had to memorize the function of the button rather than rely on the label as an indicator.

A complete transcript of the subjective comments is contained in reference [4].

Subjective Workload

The subjects were required to fly straight and level at a constant speed while performing the user interface tasks to better simulate the conditions under which these displays will be used. The NASA Task Load Index (TLX) was used to determine the subjects’ workload that included both the flying and user interface tasks. Since the flying tasks and flight displays were identical with the exception of the user interface, the difference in workload can be attributed to the user interface. Additional information regarding the NASA Task Load Index can be found in reference [5]. Version C was rated as having the lowest workload although all three displays were within two standard deviations indicating no statistically significant difference among displays as shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14. Mean Composite NASA-TLX Rating

Flying Tasks

Each subject was assigned to fly 295 degrees, 120 knots and 3000 feet while simultaneously performing the required user interface tasks. The subjects’ heading, airspeed and altitude were recorded throughout the evaluation and a statistical analysis was performed to determine if there was any statistical difference between the displays. No correlation was found ($p > 0.05$), indicating that although performance in completing tasks on the interface varied between formats, this did not translate into an effect on flying performance.

GOMS Key Level Model Predictions

To validate the use of the GOMS key level model in this application, the predicted execution times were compared to the observed execution times. Only error free tasks were compared since errors require more control inputs preventing direct comparison. Predicted execution time was calculated using the following values from reference [6]:

Keying (K) = 0.5 sec

Homing (H) = 0.4 sec

Mentally Preparing (M) = 1.35 sec

The time required to select a value using a dual-concentric knob was determined from repeated trials by different individuals to determine an average value.

Turning of Dual Concentric Knob (T) = 3.8 sec

The accuracy of the predictions can be seen graphically in Figure 15, which plots the predicted execution time versus the observed execution time.

The error bars indicate one standard error from the mean observed execution time. For each task the standard error of estimation of the population mean for samples of size "n" was determined as $SE = SD / (n)^{1/2}$. In addition, the percentage of prediction error for each task was calculated as follows:

$$\text{Pred. Error} = (T_{\text{calc}} - T_{\text{obs}}) / T_{\text{calc}}$$

where T_{calc} is the calculated or predicted time and T_{obs} is the mean observed time for the task. Comparing the time per task calculated from the model with the observed times gives an RMS (root mean square) error of 30% of the average predicted execution time. RMS error is determined as follows:

$$\text{RMS}(e) = (\sum e_i^2 / N)^{1/2}$$

where e_i is the prediction error on the i th unit task and "N" is the number of unit tasks [7]. A

value of 30% is comparable to the RMS error measurements achieved by Card, Moran and Newell [7] during their initial validation of the keystroke-level model as applied to text editors. This error can be interpreted as the average model error. 30% is high; however predicting execution times for individual tasks is a stringent test. If the unit of prediction were all of the tasks rather than the unit tasks the overall error would be less since the high and low predictions of the unit tasks would tend to cancel each other [7]. The predicted execution time is generally slightly larger than the observed time.

With one exception, the relative execution times of the tasks remained the same for the observed execution times. In other words, if the implementation of a task in Version A was predicted to take longer than the implementation of the same task in Versions B and C, it usually did when actually used. The exception was the implementation of the baro setting task in Version C. It is possible that the added complexity of the automatic mode change contributed to this increase in execution time.

Figure 15. Predicted vs. Observed Execution Times

The GOMS KLM proved useful in determining the relative execution time for various implementations of a task. It was also fairly accurate at determining the actual task execution time. These can be important discriminators when choosing between implementations, however the limitation of the model is its inability to predict error rates. Often error rates are more critical than execution times. The KLM must be applied in conjunction with judgment concerning potential sources of error for various implementations. The advantage of the KLM is that it can be used quantitatively to evaluate design ideas early in the design process without the need for a running system. Also it can be easily applied in conjunction with other methods to fully evaluate a design. The Keystroke-Level Model proved to be an effective, complementary design tool.

Recommendations

In all cases the statistically significant results indicate that the implementations of Versions B and C were improvements over Version A. Unfortunately, discrimination between Versions B and C could not be made during this evaluation due to the implemented hardware constraints that prevented full implementation of the configurations.

An analysis of the errors and subjective comments from the test participants reveals potential improvements to Versions B and C. These recommended improvements are as follows:

- Highlight the standby and auxiliary navigation sources with a box when changing the format or source (as in Version A)
- Provide the options when changing the standby format and auxiliary sources (as in Version A)
- Highlight and enlarge the parameter being changed by the knob i.e. the heading bug digital readout when in heading mode
- Increase the font size of the range scale for improved visibility and readability
- In addition, several label changes are recommended. These label changes implemented in Version B are illustrated in Figure 10.

- Change the “HSI SRC” label to “NAV SRC” and annunciate the selected source i.e. “NAV1”
- Change the “SRC SEL” label to “SWAP”
- Annunciate the current format of the “SBY FMT” i.e. “RMI”
- Change the “AUX BRG” label to “AUX SRC” and annunciate the current source i.e. “GPS1”
- Change the “MAP LVL” label to “Declutter” and add a state level indicator such as 1 through 5

Conclusions

The goal of this effort was the design, development and assessment of the user interface for the Phase I primary flight display/horizontal situation indicator. This included both hardware and software aspects of the user interface. Through the use of a structured design process, this goal was achieved with a new integrated hardware-software user interface. Multiple iterations were key to satisfying the requirements and gaining concurrence from the various design groups. Flexibility was also needed to achieve a balance between technical requirements and the corporate top-level business strategy for a competitive product. The generation of unbiased quantitative and qualitative data through human subject evaluation was an indispensable part of the design process. This can prevent costly oversights and modifications later in the process as well as aid in certification. Ultimately this effort will positively affect the first practical general aviation Highway-in-the-Sky flight display and serve as an example of multiple best practices that can be implemented in future product development efforts.

Improvements to the user interface were made in several areas including task execution time, accuracy and a subjective comparison of ease of use. Over the six tasks common to all three versions, the mean task execution time for the demonstration configuration (Version A) was 37.6 seconds compared with 23.6 seconds and 22.2 seconds for Versions B and C respectively. In addition the accuracy of setting the standby NAV format task was significantly better in Versions B and C than in Version A. In a redundant paired

comparison of the three versions based upon ease of use, Versions B and C were significantly better than Version A.

Several general principles can be drawn from the superior performance of Versions B and C over Version A that may be useful in future design efforts.

- Submenus should be avoided whenever possible. They can increase complexity and execution time. Also submenus can hide functions from the user.
- Hidden or non-intuitive interactions should be avoided such as the interaction between the knob mode selection and NAV display selection when setting a course in Version A.
- Confine tasks to as few different controls as possible. In Versions B and C tasks were executed with a maximum of two different controls. Versions A often required three different controls to be manipulated.
- Group like functions together whenever possible.
- Less options and/or functionality can reduce complexity.

The application of the GOMS Keystroke-Level Model to primary flight display user interface design was validated through a human subject evaluation. The GOMS KLM proved useful in determining the relative execution time for various implementations of a task. It was also fairly accurate at determining the actual task execution time. These can be important discriminators when choosing between implementations, however the limitation of the model is its inability to predict error rates. Often error rates are more critical than execution times. The KLM must be applied in conjunction with judgment concerning potential sources of error for various implementations. The advantage of the KLM is that it can be used quantitatively to evaluate design ideas early in the design process without the need for a running system. Also it can be easily applied in conjunction with other methods to fully evaluate a design. The Keystroke-Level Model proved to be an effective, complementary design tool.

References

- [1] Campbell, C., 2001, *Advanced Integrated General Aviation Primary Flight Display User Interface Design, Development and Assessment*, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Boston, MA, Chapter 5: Hardware Interface Development, pp. 28-42.
- [2] Campbell, C., 2001, *Advanced Integrated General Aviation Primary Flight Display User Interface Design, Development and Assessment*, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Boston, MA, Chapter 6: Software Interface Development, pp. 43-69.
- [3] Hansman, R., L. Yang, June 27-29, 1995, Application of the Analytic Hierarchy Process for Making Subjective Comparisons Between Multiple Automation/Display Options, *Proceedings of the 6th IFAC/IFIP/IFORS/IEA Symposium*. Cambridge, MA.
- [4] Campbell, C., 2001, *Advanced Integrated General Aviation Primary Flight Display User Interface Design, Development and Assessment*, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Boston, MA, Appendix D: Subjective Data, pp. 115-127.
- [5] Campbell, C., 2001, *Advanced Integrated General Aviation Primary Flight Display User Interface Design, Development and Assessment*, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Boston, MA, Appendix E: MASA-TLX Information, pp. 128-131.
- [6] Campbell, C., 2001, *Advanced Integrated General Aviation Primary Flight Display User Interface Design, Development and Assessment*, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Boston, MA, Chapter 6: Software Interface Development, pp. 51.
- [7] Card, S., T. Moran, A. Newell, 1983, *The Psychology of Human-Computer Interaction*, Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, Inc., Mahwah, New Jersey.